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Review Article

A Review On HPLC Analytical Method And Validation For Determination Of Sitagliptin Phosphate In Bulk And Different Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

A new simple, rapid, specific, accurate, precise and novel Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method has been developed for the estimation of Sitagliptin Phosphate in the pharmaceutical dosage form. The chromatographic separation for Sitagliptin was achieved with mobile phase containing methanol, ThermoScientific C18 column, (250x4.6 particle size of 5 μ) at room temperature and UV detection at 267 nm. The compounds were eluted in the isocratic mode at a flow rate of 1ml/min. The retention time of Sitagliptin was 2.37min. The above method was validated in terms of linearity, accuracy, precision, LOD, LOQ, interday, intraday, selectivity, range, stability and robustness in accordance with ICH guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

SITAGLIPTIN PHOSPHATE

Diabetes mellitus is a common disease characterized by hyperglycemia, excessive thirst, frequent urination, excessive hunger, general body malaise, and weakness due to perturbed metabolism of fat, carbohydrates, and protein. Cancer and heart disease are killer illnesses that currently afflict the population more rapidly because of their higher prevalence and link to a greater likelihood of morbidity and mortality. The major classes of oral anti-diabetic drugs include

sulfonylureas, glinides, biguanides, thiazolidinediones, α -glucosidase inhibitors, and dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) blockers.[1] The DPP-4 enzyme degrades the incretins glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1), a gastrointestinal hormone secreted in response to eating. To prevent GLP-1 breakdown, sitagliptin phosphate increases insulin discharge by suppressing glucagon release from the α cells in the pancreas, thereby regulating blood sugar levels.[2]

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Drug Profile:

Sr. No	Parameters	Description
1	Category	Antidiabetic drug of the dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitor class
2	Structure	
3	Chemical Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ F ₆ N ₅ O ₅ P
4	IUPAC Name	(2R)-4-Oxo-4-[3-(trifluoromethyl)-5,6-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]pyrazin-7(8H)-yl]-1-(2,4,5-trifluorophenyl)butan-2-amine
5	Molecular Weight	505.31 gm/mol
6	Characteristic	White to Off white, crystalline, Non hygroscopic powder
7	Solubility	Soluble in Methanol, water and slightly soluble in ethanol
8	CDSO Approval	03-07-2010

HIGH-PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY[4]

Another name for high performance liquid chromatography is high pressure liquid chromatography. It is a well-liked analytical method for figuring out, identifying, and quantifying each component of a combination. HPLC is a sophisticated method of liquid chromatography in columns. The early 20th century saw the discovery of liquid chromatography as an analytical approach that was first used to the separation of colored substances. This is the origin of the terms "chromatography," which means "color," and "graphy," which means "writing." A crude method of chromatographic separation was employed by Russian botanist Mikhail S. T-Swett to separate plant pigment mixtures into their individual components. The foundation of every chromatographic separation is the pigments' interaction with a stationary phase, which is how he separated the pigments. In his separation, the solvent served as the mobile phase,

and he employed powdered chalk and aluminum as the stationary phase. Because HPLC operates at considerably higher pressures (50 bar to 350 bar), it may be distinguished from classical ("low weight") liquid chromatography. On the other hand, the portable stage in conventional liquid chromatography usually relies on gravity to move it through the segment. Column section measurements range between 2.1 and 4.6 mm in diameter and between 30 and 250 mm in length due to the minimal sample quantity that is isolated in scientific HPLC. Furthermore, smaller sorbent particles (2 µm to 50 µm in normal molecule size) are used in the production of HPLC segments. Because of its ability to identify components while separating mixtures, HPLC has a high determining or resolving power, making it a popular chromatographic technique. HPLC provides advantages such as simultaneous analysis and high resolution.

- High Sensitivity

- Repeatability is good.
- A small sample size.
- Analysis conditions are moderate.
- Easy to fractionate and purify the sample.

Fig. 2: High-performance liquid chromatography[4]

TYPES OF HPLC

HPLC types are typically determined by the phase system employed in the procedure. The following kinds of HPLC are commonly employed in the analysis

1. Normal Phase HPLC is a process that separates analytes depending on their polarity. NP-HPLC has a polar stationary phase and a non-polar mobile phase. As a result, the stationary phase is normally silica, while the mobile phases are often hexane, methylene chloride, chloroform, diethyl ether, and combinations of these. As a result, polar samples remain on the polar surface of the column packing for longer than less polar materials.

2. Reverse-phase chromatography:

An aqueous, moderately polar mobile phase and a non-polar stationary phase make up reverse phase HPLC, also known as RPC or RP-HPLC. Hydrophobic interactions, which arise from repulsive forces between a polar eluent, the comparatively non-polar analyte, and the non-polar stationary phase, are the basis for RPC's operation. When the analyte molecule associates with the ligand in the aqueous eluent, its binding to the stationary phase is proportional to the contact surface area around the non-polar region of the molecule.

3. Ion exchange chromatography:

In this method, solute ions are attracted to charged sites that are attached to the stationary phase, which results in retention. The same-charged ions are not included. Water purification, ligand-exchange chromatography, protein ion-exchange chromatography, high-pH anion-exchange chromatography of carbohydrates and oligosaccharides, and other applications are common uses for this type of chromatography.

4. Size exclusion chromatography (SEC):

also referred to as gel filtration or gel permeation chromatography, is a technique used to primarily separate particles according to size. Determining the quaternary and tertiary structures of proteins and amino acids is another beneficial application of it. This method is frequently employed to determine the molecular weight of polysaccharides.

5. Bio-affinity chromatography:

A method of separation based on the particular, reversible interactions that ligands and proteins have. In a bio-affinity matrix, ligands are covalently bonded to solid support, retaining proteins that interact with the column-bound ligands. Proteins attached to a bio-affinity column can be extracted in two ways:

- Bio-specific elution involves using a free ligand in the elution solution to compete with column-bound ligands.
- A particular elution is characterized by changes in pH, salt, and other factors that impair the protein's interaction with column-bound substrates.
- Normal Phase: hydrocarbon-free, organic mobile phase
- Non-aqueous silica gel
- Adsorption
- Aqueous mobile phase in reverse phase (C8, C18)

Dividends

- Water-based ion-exchange mobile phase
- Aqueous mobile phase-molecular sieve
- Dimensions

e. The detector

- Particular

Absorbance

- Fluorescence
- Electrochemical
- Indefinite
- Index of Refraction

Radioactivity

Conductivity

Because of the selectivity of the contact, affinity chromatography may achieve very high purification rates in a single step (10 - 1000-fold).

Instrumentation of HPLC[5]

- Solvent reservoir and pump
- under high pressure (1000–5000 psi)
- An injector

Reduced pressure:

cease the flow

Value at high pressure

- Desk

LITERATURE REVIEW:

METHODS OF SITAGLIPTIN PHOSPHATE (ONE-TIME ASPECT):

Sr. No.	Drug	Method	Description
1	Sitagliptin in large quantities and in pharmaceutical form	The UV Spectrophotometric Approach	Wavelength of detection: 267 nm 0.1 N HCl is the solvent. Range of linearity: 20–100% Coefficient of correlation: 0.998 %Recovery: 96-49%
2	In pharmaceutical preparations, sitagliptin	The UV Spectrophotometric Approach	Wavelength of detection: 430 nm Range of concentration: 5–25 µg/ml Molar absorptivity apparente: 1.067x10 ⁴ Lmol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ Coefficient of correlation: 0.9998 %RSD: 1.13% The detection limit is 1.947 µg/ml. 5.90µg/ml is the quantitative limit.
3	Both in bulk and in formulation, sitagliptin	UV Spectrophotometric technique: First order derivative method	Sitagliptin's λ _{max} in methanol and water is 267 nm. The trough's maximum amplitude was 275 nm. Range of linearity: 10–60 µg/ml Correlation value: 0.9998 percent Drug content: 99.19% Recovery percentage: 98.54%–99.98% .

4	Bulk Sitagliptin Phosphate and pharmaceutical preparations	The UV Spectrophotometric Approach	Absorption maximum: 400 nm Range of linearity: 2–10µg/ml Methanol is the solvent. 0.139µg/ml is the limit of detection (LOD). 0.422µg/ml is the limit of quantitation (LOQ). Recovery Rate on Average: 98.72 - 108.2%.
5	Sitagliptin in the Plasma of Humans	RP-HPLC Technique	Wavelength of detection: 267 nm Stationary Phase: 150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5µm Intersil C18 column Phase of mobility: Acetonitrile: Methanol: O-phosphoric acid-pH 4.0 buffer (2:3:5 v/v) Rate of flow: 1.0 mL/min Range of linearity: 25–125µg/mL
6	Sitagliptin in Human Plasma	The LC-MS method involves liquid chromatography and tandem mass spectrometry. Spectrometry method using Liquid-Liquid Extraction	Range of linearity: 0.1–250 ng/mL 0.1 ng/mL is the lower limit of quantitation (LLOQ). Transitions in multiple reaction monitoring (MRM): m/z (Sitagliptin): 408 – 235 310–148 m/z (internal standard) Each sample will run for two minutes.
7	Sitagliptin in Human Plasma	Using the LC-MS/MS technique with protein precipitation and simultaneous mass spectroscopic analysis	Waters Atlantis Hilic Silica column (2.1 mm × 50 mm, 3 µm) is in the stationary phase. ACN/H ₂ O (80/20, v/v) with 10 mM NH ₄ Ac (pH 4.7) is the mobile phase. Transitions in multiple reaction monitoring: sitagliptin (m/z 408 → 235) and For IS, 412 → 239. Quantitation's lower limit: 1 ng/mL Range of linearity: 1–1000 ng/mL
8	The unit dosage forms and API for sitagliptin phosphate	Try the extractive method with a spectrophotometer.	The drug's complexation with bromothymol forms the basis of the methods. Bromo Cresol Green (BCG-Method B) and Blue (BTB Method A) Removal Chloroform is the solvent. Maximas of absorbance 412 nm is Method A. 419 nm is Method B. Range of linearity: Procedure A: 25–125 µg/ml Procedure B: 10–50 µg/ml

9	Sitagliptin phosphate can cause formulation and spiked urine.	Method of Spectrofluorimetry	Wavelength of fluorescence: 297 nm Range of linearity: 0.6–10 μ g mL ⁻¹ The detection limit is 78.782 ng/ml. Quantification limit: 238.735 ng/ml% Sitagliptin phosphate content in tablet form: 93.34–102.67%.
10	Phospholiptin Sitagliptin in Pharmaceutical formulation	A Specific Sensor Potentiometric Approach	Responses that are linear: 1 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁵ to 1 $\times$ 10 ⁻² M, with a 40.9 mV/decade slope 1 $\times$ 10 ⁻¹ M is the stock solution. Solutions in use: (1 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁷ to 1 $\times$ 10 ⁻² M) 40.9% slope (mV/decade) Cross-section: 260.9 mV LOD: 2.0 x 10 ⁻⁶ (M) Reaction Time: 30 Seconds pH Range of Operation: 4–7 .
11	Sitagliptin in Substances Used in Biology	MAP stands for molecularly imprinted biomimetic materials (polymers) sensors for Quantitative Transduction Technique Analysis of flow injection (FIA)	pH 5 in an acidic solution Sensors display Concentration ranges: 1.0x10 ⁻² molL ⁻¹ (MAA)–5.0x10 ⁻⁶ 1.0x10 ⁻² mol L ⁻¹ (2-VP) – 1.0x10 ⁻⁵ Slopes: decade-1, 52.7–40.5 mV Range linear (mol L ⁻¹): MIP/MAA: 5.0x10 ⁻⁶ MAA+TPB/MIP: 5.0x10 ⁻⁶ 1.0x10 ⁻⁵ is MIP/2-VP. VP+TPB-: 2.5x10 ⁻⁶ MIP/2
12	Sitagliptin Hydrochloride for Encased Tablets	Dissolution Technique Using In Vivo Data to Enhance Medium Perceptiveness	Phosphate buffer at pH 6.8 900 mL of dissolving media at 37 $\pm$ 1 $^{\circ}$ C in temperature Equipment: paddle RPM (revolving speed): 50. Range of linearity: 10.0-70.0% μ g/mL Mean recovery accuracy: 98.51%.
METHOD DESCRIBED FOR SITAGLIPTIN PHOSPHATE (WITH A COMBINATION):			
13	Metformin and Sitagliptin in tablet and bulk dose forms	UV Spectrophotometric Technique	Sitagliptin's detection wavelength is 266 nm, while metformin HCl's is 232 nm. Hydrogenated distillate The quality of being linear 25–225 μ g/ml of sitagliptin HCl metformin: 2–12 μ g/ml %Healing: Sitagliptin percentage: 99.64% HCl metformin: 98.98%

14	Metformin and Sitagliptin in tablet and bulk dose forms	RP-HPLC Technique	<p>Wavelength of detection: 215 nm</p> <p>Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate (pH-8.5): Methanol (50:50 v/v) is the mobile phase. Hypersil BDS C18 Column (100 mm, 4.6 mm, 5 µm) in the stationary phase</p> <p>Range of linearity: 50–1500% Sitagliptin Metformin: 50–150 percent</p> <p>Rate of flow: 1.0 ml/min</p> <p>Sitagliptin's detection limit is 0.07 µg/ml.</p> <p>Methylcobalamine: 0.08 µg/ml</p> <p>Sitagliptin's limit of quantification is 2.3 µg/ml.</p> <p>2.6 µg/ml of metformin HCl.</p>
15	Sitagliptin Phosphate with Metformin Hydrochloride in a formulation	RP-HPLC Technique	<p>Wavelength of detection: 266 nm</p> <p>Phase of Mobility: Methanol: 70:30 v/v potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer</p> <p>Stationary Phase: 250 × 4.6 mm, 5µm Li-chromosphere 100 C18 ODS, Hibar-240 column</p> <p>Range of linearity: sitagliptin Potassium: 10–50 µg/mL</p> <p>HCl metformin: 20–100 µg/mL</p> <p>Rate of flow: 1.0 ml/min Retention durations: 6.1 minutes for sitagliptin phosphate 4.9 minutes for metformin HCl</p> <p>Limit of Detection: Phosphate of sitagliptin: 0.016 µg/ml Methylcobalamine: 0.14 µg/ml</p> <p>Limitation on Quantification: Phosphate of sitagliptin: 0.048 µg/ml Hydrochlorothiazide: 0.42 µg/ml.</p>
16	Metformin with Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate tablets containing hydrochloride	Stability signaling the RP HPLC technique	<p>Beam width of detection: 245 nm</p> <p>Acetonitrile: Ammonium acetate buffer (pH - 4.5) in a 70:30 v/v mobile phase</p> <p>Stage of Stationarity: {25 cm, 4.6 mm, 5 µm} Supelco column</p> <p>range of linearity: 10%–50% of a milligram</p> <p>Metformin: 0.5–1 mg/ml</p> <p>0.8 milliliters per minute of flow</p> <p>%Healing: Sitagliptin: 99% 100.6% of metformin HCl</p>
17	Large doses of Sitagliptin and Metformin dose form for medications	Stability Signifying RP HPLC Technique	<p>205 nm is the wavelength of detection using a photodiode array detector.</p> <p>OPA buffer in mobile phase: acetonitrile (80:20 v/v)</p> <p>Agilent CN (250mm x 4.6mm, 5µm) column in</p>

			<p>the stationary phase</p> <p>Range of linearity: Methyl-25-750 µg/ml 3-75µg/ml Sitagliptin Rate of flow: 1.0 ml/min</p>
18	Tablets containing sitagliptin phosphate monohydrate and metformin hydrochloride	UPLC Methodology	<p>Wavelength of detection: 210 nm</p> <p>Phase of Mobility: 10 mM Dihydrogen phosphate of potassium: 2 mM Acetonitrile is the sodium salt of hexane 1 sulfonic acid.</p> <p>UPLC BEH C8 column (100 x 2.1 mm i.d, 1.7 µm) in the stationary phase</p> <p>Rate of flow: 0.2 ml/min</p> <p>Limit of Detection: 0.2 µg/ml of sitagliptin Clinical metformin: 0.06 µg/ml</p> <p>Limitation on Quantification: 0.7 µg/ml of sitagliptin 0.2 µg/ml of metformin hydrochloride</p>
19	Sitagliptin Phosphate and Metformin Hydrochloride	UPLC Method	<p>Detection wavelength: 220 nm</p> <p>Mobile Phase: Isocratic elution (methanol 20%), pH (3.5)</p> <p>Stationary Phase: Symmetry C₁₈column (100 mm × 2.1 mm, 2.2 µm)</p> <p>Linearity range: Sitagliptin: 2-12µg ml⁻¹ Metformin: 5-35µg ml⁻¹</p>
20	Metformin Hydrochloride and Sitagliptin Phosphate in Tablet Dosage Form	HPTLC Method	<p>Stationary Phase: Silica gel 60 F254 plates</p> <p>Mobile phase: Butanol: Water: Glacial acetic acid (6: 2: 2, v/v/v)</p> <p>Detection wavelength: 227 nm</p> <p>Rf value: Metformin hydrochloride: 0.35 ± 0.01 Sitagliptin phosphate: 0.75 ± 0.01</p> <p>Limits of Detection: Metformin hydrochloride: 13.05 ng/L Sitagliptin phosphate: 2.65 ng/L</p> <p>Limits of Quantitation: Metformin hydrochloride: 39.56 ng/L Sitagliptin phosphate: 8.03 ng/L</p>
21	Sitagliptin and Metformin Hydrochloride in Bulk Drug and Formulation	HPTLC Method	<p>Stationary Phase: TLC plates precoated with silica gel 60F254</p> <p>Mobile phase: Methanol: Ammonia: Glacial acetic acid (9.4:0.4:0.2 v/v/v)</p> <p>Detection and TLC scanner wavelength: 214 nm</p>

			<p>Concentration range: Sitagliptin: 100–1100 ng band-1 Metformin hydrochloride: 1000–11000 ng band 1</p> <p>Limits of Detection: Sitagliptin: 7.08 ng band-1 Metformin hydrochloride: 19.31 ng band-1</p> <p>Limits of Quantitation: Sitagliptin: 21.82 ng band-1 Metformin hydrochloride: 58.51 ng band-1</p>
22	Metformin and Sitagliptin in Human Plasma	LC-MS-MS Method and Its Application in a Bioequivalence Study	<p>Solvent: Acetonitrile Stationary Phase: SCX column Linearity range: Metformin: 10–2,206 ng/mL Sitagliptin: 3–800.5 ng/mL Mean recovery: Metformin: 92% Sitagliptin: 104.5%</p>
23	Sitagliptin and Metformin in Pharmaceutical Preparations	Capillary Zone Electrophoresis and its Application to Human Plasma Analysis	<p>Detection wavelength: 203 nm Stationary Phase: Separation in fused silica capillary (50.0 cm total length and 43.0 cm effective length, 49 μm i.d.) Mobile phase: Buffer containing 60 mm phosphate buffer at pH 4.0 Temperature of the capillary cartridge: 25°C Internal standard (IS): Phenformin Linearity ranges: Sitagliptin: 10–100 μg/mL Metformin: 50–500 μg/mL Limits of detection: Sitagliptin: 0.49 μg/mL Metformin: 2.11 μg/mL Limits of quantification: Sitagliptin: 1.48 μg/mL Metformin: 6.39 μg/mL</p>
24	Sitagliptin in Binary Mixture with Metformin and Ternary Mixture with Metformin and Sitagliptin Alkaline Degradation Product	Spectrofluorometric and Spectrophotometric Methods	<p>The zero-order spectrophotometric method for STG: 50–300 μg mL⁻¹ The first derivative spectrophotometric method For MET: 2–12 μg mL⁻¹ For STG: 50–300 μg mL⁻¹ Peak amplitude: 246.5 nm and 275 nm Metformin: 2–12 μg mL⁻¹ Peak amplitudes: 232 nm and 239 nm The Fluorometric method: 0.25–110 μg mL⁻¹</p>
25	Metformin and Three Gliptins in Pharmaceutical	RP-HPLC Method & Application to Stability Studies	<p>Stationary Phase: Fast monolithic column Mobile phase: Mixture of Sodium</p>

	Formulations		<p>dihydrogen phosphate, Sodium dodecyl sulphate and Acetonitrile</p> <p>Detection wavelength: Metformin, Vildagliptin & Sitagliptin: 208 nm Metformin & Linagliptin: 228 nm</p> <p>Flow rate: 2.5 mL/min</p> <p>Linearity range: Metformin: 10–100 µg/mL and 50–400 µg/mL Vildagliptin & Sitagliptin : 1–10 µg/mL Linagliptin: 0.25–2.0 µg/mL</p> <p>Retention time: Metformin: 0.78 and 0.76 min Vildagliptin: 1.18 min Sitagliptin: 3.83 min Linagliptin: 2.65 min</p> <p>LOD (µg/mL): Metformin: 0.01 and 0.09 Vildagliptin: 0.03 Sitagliptin: 0.02 Linagliptin: 0.02</p> <p>LOQ (µg/mL): Metformin: 0.04 and 0.29 Vildagliptin: 0.097 Sitagliptin: 0.064 Linagliptin: 0.067</p>
26	Sitagliptin and Pioglitazone in combination of drugs	UV Spectrophotometric Method	<p>Detection wavelength: Sitagliptin: 267nm Pioglitazone HCl: 269nm</p> <p>Solvent: Double Distilled water, 0.1N HCl, Methanol</p> <p>Linearity: Sitagliptin: 20-120 µg/ml Pioglitazone HCl: 2.5-25 µg/ml</p> <p>%Recovery: Sitagliptin: 101.3±0.88% Pioglitazone HCl: 94.5±3.47%</p>
27	Sitagliptin and Pioglitazone in pharmaceutical dosage form	RP-HPLC Method	<p>Detection wavelength: Sitagliptin: 267nm Pioglitazone HCl: 225nm</p> <p>Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile: potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH - 3) (30:70v/v)</p> <p>Stationary Phase: C₁₈ column {250 mm, 4.6 mm, 5 µm}</p> <p>Linearity range: Sitagliptin: 20-60 µg/ml Pioglitazone HCl: 6-14 µg/ml</p> <p>Flow rate: 1.0ml/min</p>
28	Gliclazide And Sitagliptin	UV	Solvent: Methanol

	Phosphate Monohydrate In Bulk And Pharmaceutical Dosage Form	Spectrophotometric Method	Detection wavelength: Gliclazide: 226 nm Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate: 267 nm Linearity range: Gliclazide: 7-27 µg/ml Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate: 20-100 µg/ml
29	Gliclazide And Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate In Bulk And Tablet Dosage Form	RP-HPLC Method	Stationary phase: Phenomenex Luna (C18) A 100RP Column (250mm x 4.6mm x 5µm) Injection volume: 20µl Mobile phase: Water: Acetonitrile (40:60 v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min Retention time: Gliclazide: 3.268 min Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate: 2.260 min Detection wavelength: 253nm Linearity range: Gliclazide: 5-25 µg/ml Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate: 20-100 µg/ml Percentage Assay: Gliclazide: 100.01 Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate: 99.3 Limit of detection: Gliclazide: 0.4364 µg/ml Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate: 0.6 µg/ml Limit of quantification: Gliclazide: 1.3232 µg/ml Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate: 1.9 µg/ml
30	Simvastatin and Sitagliptin in combined dosage form	RP-HPLC Method	Detection wavelength: 266nm PDA detector Mobile Phase: Methanol: Water (25:75, v/v) Stationary Phase: Agilent C8 column {250 x 4.6mm, 5 µm} Linearity range: Sitagliptin: 20-120µg/ml Simvastatin:10-50µg/ml Flow rate: 1 ml/min Retention time: Sitagliptin: 3.227min Simvastatin: 15.760 min
31	Sitagliptin Phosphate And Simvastatin In Bulk And Tablet Dosage Form	RP-HPLC Method	Detection wavelength: 250nm Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile, Methanol, and 10 mM Phosphate buffer (65:25:10 % v/v/v) pH 4 adjusted with orthophosphoric acid Stationary Phase: aHi-Q Sil C18(250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm Particle size) column Linearity range: Sitagliptin: 20-120µg/ml Simvastatin: 10-50µg/ml Flow rate: 1.2 ml/min Retention time:

			<p>Sitagliptin: 2.2 min Simvastatin: 6.8 min Linearity range: Sitagliptin: 100-600 µg/ml Simvastatin: 20-120 µg/ml</p>
32	Simvastatin and Sitagliptin in tablet dosage form	Stability indicating RP-HPLC Method	<p>Detection wavelength: 252 nm Mobile Phase: 0.05M phosphate buffer (pH 4±0.02 adjusted with o-phosphoric acid): Acetonitrile (70:30 v/v) Stationary Phase: BDS HypersilC18, (250mm × 4.6mm × 5µm) column. Linearity range: Sitagliptin: 20-120µg/ml Simvastatin: 10-50µg/ml Flow rate: 1.0 ml/min Total run time: 10 minutes Linearity range: Sitagliptin: 7.5-52.5µg/ ml Simvastatin: 3.5-10.5µg/ ml Amount of drugs present in the formulation (Juvisync): Sitagliptin: 99.81 ± 0.73 Simvastatin: 99.97 ± 0.61</p>
33	Simvastatin and Sitagliptin Tablets	Stability indicating RP-HPLC Method	<p>Detection wavelength: 253nm PDA detector Mobile Phase: Methanol: Water (70:30, v/v) Stationary Phase: Qualisil BDS C8 column {250x 4.6mm, 5 µm} Linearity range: Sitagliptin: 20-150µg/ml Simvastatin: 8-60µg/ml Flow rate: 1 ml/min Retention time: Sitagliptin: 4.3min Simvastatin: 30.4 min</p>
34	Sitagliptin And Simvastatin In Pharmaceutical Formulation	HPTLC Method	<p>Stationary Phase: Merck TLC aluminum sheets of silicagelG60 F254 with a thickness of 200 µm. Mobile phase: Ethyl acetate: Toluene: Methanol (6:2:2 v/v/v) Detection wavelength by densitometry:254 nm Rf value: Sitagliptin: 0.6 +0.02 Simvastatin: 0.3+0.02 Concentration range: Sitagliptin: 2-6 µg/spot Simvastatin: 0.2-0.6 µg/spot</p>
35	Sitagliptin vildagliptin in bulk and dosage form	UV spectroscopy (based on charge transfer complexes)	<p>Detection wavelength: 461nm Sitagliptin: 461nm (with DDQ)</p>

			837nm (with TCNQ) 555nm (with p-chloranil) Vildagliptin: 486nm (with DDQ) 838nm (with TCNQ) 555nm (with p-chloranil) Solvent: Sitagliptin: Methanol (with DDQ) Methanol (with TCNQ) DMF (with p-chloranil) Vildagliptin: Acetonitrile (with DDQ) Methanol (with TCNQ) DMF (with p-chloranil) Linearity: Sitagliptin: 50-300µg/ml (with DDQ) 20-120µg/ml (with TCNQ) 100-900µg/ml (with p-chloranil) Vildagliptin: 50-300µg/ml (with DDQ) 10-85µg/ml (with TCNQ) 50-350µg/ml (with p-chloranil)
36	Sitagliptin, Metformin and Atorvastatin in Pure form and in Pharmaceutical Formulation	RP-HPLC Method	Detection wavelength: 254nm Mobile Phase: Mix buffer: Methanol (30:70 v/v) Stationary Phase: HyperSil GOL (150mm x 4.6mm, 5µm) column Internal Std.: Quetiapine Flow rate: 1.0 ml/min Linearity range: Sitagliptin: 3.125-100µg/ml Metformin: 0.625-25µg/ml Atorvastatin: 3.125-10µg/ml Retention time: Sitagliptin: 3.384 min Metformin: 2.640 min Atorvastatin: 4.837 min Quetiapine (IS): 6.000 min Limit of Detection: Sitagliptin: 0.82 µg/ml Metformin: 0.4µg/ml Atorvastatin: 0.09µg/ml Limit of Quantification: Sitagliptin: 2.46 µg/ml Metformin: 1.2µg/ml Atorvastatin: 0.27µg/ml
37	Metformin,	Liquid	Detection wavelength: 220 nm

	Pioglitazone, Sitagliptin, Repaglinide, Glibenclamide and Gliclazide	Chromatography c-c Method & Application for Counterfeit Drug Analysis	Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile (solution A) and buffer (solution B); the latter was composed of 0.05 M MKP and 0.01M SOS, pH adjusted to 3.55 by 85% ortho-phosphoric acid Stationary Phase: Kromasil 100-C18 (30 × 0.4 cm, 10µm) Flow rate: 0.85 ml/min Injection volume: 20 µl. Run time for each injection: 20 minutes. Retention time: Metformin:2.24 Sitagliptin: 3.13 Pioglitazone: 6.3 Gliclazide: 7.41 Glibenclamide: 8.41 Repaglinide: 14.32
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CONCLUSION:

The documented spectrophotometric and chromatographic techniques that were created and verified for sitagliptin estimation are shown in this review. This review led to the conclusion that, in order to increase resolution, various spectroscopic and chromatographic techniques are available for both single and combination forms of sitagliptin. Additionally, it was discovered that most chromatographic methods used a mobile phase that included phosphate buffer, methanol, and acetonitrile. It was shown that the most typical pairing of sitagliptin and metformin (JANUMET) was prevalent. To obtain a satisfactory retention time for the chromatographic technique, a flow rate of 0.8–1.5 ml/min is observed. Methanol is a popular solvent used in the majority of spectroscopic procedures. As a result, all of the techniques were discovered to be straightforward, precise, affordable, accurate, and repeatable. However, it became evident from this assessment that the Design of Expert (DOE) process might be used to improve the existing methodologies and produce more exact and accurate results.

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